

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center Target Enabling Component Bioinformatics For PTK2B

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PTK2B (Protein-Tyrosine Kinase 2-Beta) gene encodes a cytoplasmic protein tyrosine kinase which is involved in calcium-induced regulation of ion channels and activation of the MAP kinase signaling pathway. It is a member of the FAK subfamily of protein tyrosine kinases but lacks significant sequence similarity to kinases from other subfamilies. The gene expression is localized in the brain, hematopoietic and nervous systems. The encoded protein may represent an important signaling intermediate between neuropeptide-activated receptors or neurotransmitters that increase calcium flux and the downstream signals that regulate neuronal activity. It undergoes rapid tyrosine phosphorylation and activation in response to increases in the intracellular calcium concentration, nicotinic acetylcholine receptor activation, membrane depolarization, or protein kinase C activation. PTK2B plays a role in the regulation of the humoral immune response, and is required for normal levels of marginal B-cells in the spleen and normal migration of splenic B-cells. It is required for normal macrophage polarization and migration towards sites of inflammation. PTK2B is an important paralog of PTK2, both of which forms multisubunit complexes with Src and Src family members upon activation and phosphorylates Src family kinases. PTK2B is involved in multiple signaling pathways. It promotes activation of phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase and of the AKT1 signaling cascade, promotes activation of NOS3, regulates production of the cellular messenger cGMP, promotes activation of the MAP kinase signaling cascade. Cytokine and chemokines activates PTK2B. A more extensive literature review of PTK2B is in "IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center Target Enabling Resource Evaluation of Literature Compounds as PTK2b/PYK2 Chemical Probes" <https://zenodo.org/record/8322774>. In this file, results from BCB bioinformatic research are summarized.

Unlike most of the AD potential drug target genes that have been studied in our center, PTK2B is not part of the microglia coexpression module. Instead, it is found to be in the frequent coexpression

module for neuron function together with about over a thousand genes in our five [1] and eight AD patient brain transcriptomic analysis {unpublished}, as well as in the meta coexpression study of different brain regions of DLPFC, FP, IFG, STG, PHG, TCX [2]. Although it is not shown to be coexpressed with most of the core microglia genes we have studied, this gene is still a microglia marker gene [4]. It is also a known AD risk gene through GWAS study.

PTK2B is significantly down expressed in multiple bulk tissue brain RNA-seq and microarray data, which may be due to the loss of neurons in the bulk tissue samples. A more refined single cell differential expression analysis shows upregulated in the AD disease brain, and peaks in the early AD stage. This has been observed in both the excitatory and inhibitory neurons (Table-1). The protein is also significantly down expressed in the AD vs. normal brain samples.

Dataset	Log2 FoldChange	P value	Adjusted P value	Comparison	Data source
MSBB	-0.312	5.12E-11	1.00E-09	AD vs. Normal	[1]
GSE84422	-0.289	6.66E-11	4.70E-08	AD vs. Normal	[1]
ROSMAP	-0.161	3.15E-04	4.32E-03	AD vs. Normal	[1]
GSE48350	-0.267	6.02E-04	1.88E-03	AD vs. Normal	[1]
GSE5281	-0.322	7.93E-04	2.40E-03	AD vs. Normal	[1]
MSBB proteomics	-0.408	0.0215	NA	AD vs. Normal	Unpublished
Excitatory neurons	0.154	NA	2.04E-14	pathology vs no-pathology	[3]
Excitatory neurons	0.25	NA	3.09E-06	early-pathology vs no-pathology	[3]
Excitatory neurons	-0.3096	NA	3.59E-04	late-pathology vs early-pathology	[3]
Inhibitory neurons	0.3278	NA	2.48E-02	pathology vs no-pathology	[3]
Inhibitory neurons	0.5867	NA	1.53E-03	early-pathology vs no-pathology	[3]
Inhibitory neurons	-0.8789	NA	2.25E-02	late-pathology vs early-pathology	[3]

The protein-protein interaction network mining shows PTK2B mostly interacts with Src family kinases and GRB2 (Figure-1), which is the epidermal growth factor receptor binding protein.

Figure-1 PPI network of PTK2B from STRING database

Since PTK2B is also involved in glioblastoma and osteoporosis, it has been studied as potential drug target for these two diseases. The X-ray structure and selectivity assays are known and several compounds have been identified with binding affinity for this protein.

Reference:

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4. Zhang Y, et al. An RNA-Sequencing Transcriptome and Splicing Database of Glia, Neurons, and Vascular Cells of the Cerebral Corte. *J Neurosci* 2014; doi:10.1523/JNEUROSCI.1860-14